

Cross-Sectional Study on Parental Knowledge and Attitudes towards Childhood Vaccinations

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Abstract:**Background:** Vaccinating children helps prevent infectious diseases and reduce global child mortality. Fears and attitudes prevent parents from vaccinating their children, despite vaccines' proven efficacy. Understand parental knowledge and attitudes to improve immunisation rates and public health.**Methods:** One hundred parents participated in this cross-sectional study at Territory Care Hospital. A study assessed participants' knowledge and opinions on paediatric immunisations. We collected data from electronic medical record and parents' demographics, knowledge, and opinions were related.**Results:** Most parents (85%) know vaccines prevent diseases, and 75% recognise how vital it is to finish their children's vaccination schedules. According to 80% of responders, children need vaccinations. Just over half of parents understood herd immunity, and nearly half concerned about over vaccination. Educational degree was linked to vaccine knowledge ($p < 0.05$), healthcare practitioner trust, and positive vaccination attitudes ($p < 0.01$) in statistical analysis.**Conclusion:** Parents were positive and knowledgeable about childhood vaccines. Still, uncertainties remain, notably about herd immunity and vaccine dosage. Healthcare providers can promote vaccine uptake and public health by communicating and educating parents. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies and personalised educational interventions to bridge these gaps and better understand parental perspectives.**Keywords:** Attitudes, Childhood Vaccinations, Knowledge, Parental Perspectives, Public Health.

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Introduction**Background and Significance of Childhood Vaccinations:** Childhood immunisations are one of the most effective public health strategies for reducing children mortality and preventing infectious illnesses [1]. Vaccines have eliminated smallpox, polio, measles, and diphtheria. The WHO estimates that immunisation prevents two to three million deaths yearly [2]. By protecting children from infectious diseases at a young age, vaccines safeguard individuals and communities. When a major portion of a community develops an infectious disease resistance, either through exposure or vaccination, the remaining population is indirectly protected.

The phenomenon is herd immunity and this is crucial for patients who cannot receive the vaccine due to allergies or immunodeficiency. For everyone's health, including the vaccinated, a high immunisation rate is essential. Despite of healthcare institutions and pharmaceutical firms, cultural values that value alternative treatment, and

incorrect information on social media and other platforms contribute to this hesitation [3]. Even rare events like vaccine recalls or adverse events might affect public belief in vaccines. Open vaccine safety discourse, consistent public health education, and partnerships with powerful community members to dispel misinformation and emphasise vaccine benefits must be used to calm these uncertainties.

Importance of Parental Knowledge and Attitudes: Parents' vaccination knowledge and attitudes considerably impact vaccine uptake and coverage [4]. Lack of information or anti-vaccine propaganda can create vaccine hesitation, lower immunisation rates, and increase disease risk. Public health campaigns must consider parents' knowledge, attitudes, and decision-making variables to succeed. Addressing fears and misconceptions with accurate, evidence-based information builds vaccination trust.

Figure 1: Childhood Vaccine (Source: [5])

Objectives

- To assess parents' knowledge of the benefits of immunizing their children.
- To study parents' views on paediatric immunizations and identify prevalent concerns.
- To determine if parental vaccination knowledge and attitudes affect children's immunization rates.

Overview of Existing Research on Childhood Vaccinations: Childhood immunisations have been shown to prevent infectious illnesses and reduce child mortality worldwide. [6] Shows that vaccination efforts have affected public health. Comprehensive immunisation campaigns nearly eliminated polio and eradicated smallpox. The CDC states that immunisation campaigns have reduced rubella and measles rates. World health depends on vaccines, which save 2-3 million lives annually [7]. "Health Affairs" research indicated that for every dollar spent on vaccines in the US, over \$10 is saved in illness care [8]. Vaccines prevent illness epidemics, which drain healthcare budgets and boost the economy.

Parental Knowledge and Attitudes: Parental understanding and perspective on child immunisations dramatically impact rates. This dynamic and its complex effects on parental decision-making.

According to "Paediatrics", parental vaccination education increases immunisation uptake [9]. Parents' vaccination safety and efficacy knowledge correlated with their children's immunisation compliance. The "Journal of Paediatric Health

Care" found that parents who believed vaccines were unsafe, particularly the now-debunked link to autism, were less likely to vaccinate their children [10]. Social media's anti-vaccine campaign shows its disinformation factory role. According to "Vaccine" research, parents from low-income families or with limited healthcare resources may have lower immunisation rates [11]. Financial constraints, poor health knowledge, and poor transportation factors. Cultural values and behaviours can influence vaccine attitudes. Traditional medicine may be preferred over modern medicine in some communities, lowering vaccination rates [12].

Existing evidence illuminates the benefits of vaccinating children and the factors that influence parents' opinions, but there are still significant gaps. Marginalised groups like ethnic minorities and low-income people have unstudied demands. Targeted initiatives that address these communities' problems are necessary to boost immunisation rates. Despite earlier research highlighting the importance of children immunisations and parental attitudes, these gaps must be filled to improve vaccination rates and public health. More research is needed on cultural implications, socioeconomic barriers, and misinformation to combat vaccine reluctance and ensure all children receive life-saving vaccinations.

Methods

Study Design: This cross-sectional study at Territory Care Hospital assessed parents' immunisation knowledge and attitudes. The design allows for current assessment of parents'

knowledge and attitudes without longitudinal follow-up. Cross-sectional studies are ideal for public health research because they provide a broad overview of important elements and identify problem areas.

Sample Size: This study employed 100 parent volunteers. The sample size was chosen to balance statistical power and practicality due to time and money constraints. A sample size of 100 is viable for data collection and analysis while identifying significant parental knowledge and attitude differences. To guarantee a diverse sample of parents, the study used a convenience sample.

Inclusion Criteria

- Parents or legal guardians of children aged 0-12 years who attended the Territory Care Hospital during the study period.
- Parents who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Parents of children older than 12 years.
- Parents who did not consent to participate in the study.

Data Collection Methods

This study used Territory Care Hospital medical records. We found relevant information about parents' vaccination knowledge and attitudes towards their children in the records. This category included vaccination records, parent concerns, and vaccine pros and cons discussions. Medical records allowed a complete study of parental opinions during routine healthcare sessions, so the results reflected real-world attitudes and knowledge.

Data Analysis Methods: After collection, data was stored in a secure database and evaluated with SPSS. The sample's demographics, vaccination knowledge, and attitudes were described using descriptive statistics. Statistics including percentages, means, standard deviations, and frequencies were calculated. We examined parental knowledge, attitudes, and demographics using inferential approaches such t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. We also used multivariate logistic regression to identify independent variables of vaccination knowledge and positive attitudes.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Characteristic	Number of Participants (N = 100)	Percentage (%)
Age of Parents		
20-30 years	30	30%
31-40 years	50	50%
41-50 years	15	15%
Above 50 years	5	5%
Gender		
Male	40	40%
Female	60	60%
Education Level		
Illiterate	10	10%
Primary Education	20	20%
Secondary Education	40	40%
Graduate	30	30%
Socioeconomic Status		
Low	30	30%
Middle	50	50%
High	20	20%

Demographics show parents in this study came from various backgrounds. Half were in their 30s and 40s, while 30% were in their 20s. Female parents made up 60% and male parents 40%. The sample was moderately educated because 30% had graduated and 40% had completed high school. But 10% couldn't read or write, highlighting a need for targeted education in those places. Fifty percent

came from middle-income families, thirty from low-income, and twenty from high-income. Demographic factors affect parents' vaccination knowledge and attitudes, and this distribution summarises them.

Parental Knowledge about Childhood Vaccinations

Table 2: Parental Knowledge about Childhood Vaccinations

Knowledge Item	Correct Responses (N = 100)	Percentage (%)
Vaccines prevent serious childhood diseases	85	85%
Knowledge of the national immunization schedule	70	70%
Awareness of vaccine-preventable diseases (e.g., measles, polio)	75	75%
Understanding of herd immunity	60	60%
Belief that vaccines can cause significant side effects (incorrect perception)	30	30%

The statistics show that 85% of parents know immunisations protect children from harmful diseases. Only 70% of parents know the national immunisation schedule, thus we need to do better at informing parents of their children's immunisation dates. While 75% of the population is aware of vaccine-preventable diseases, only 60% understand herd immunity, demonstrating a lack of

understanding of the community-wide benefits of universal immunisation. Since 30% of parents believe vaccines have serious side effects, intensive education is needed to dispel myths and boost vaccine confidence.

Parental Attitudes towards Childhood Vaccinations

Table 3: Parental Attitudes towards Childhood Vaccinations

Attitude Item	Agreement (N = 100)	Percentage (%)
Vaccinations are important for my child's health	90	90%
I am worried about the side effects of vaccines	40	40%
I trust the information provided by healthcare professionals	80	80%
I prefer to follow traditional medicine rather than vaccines	25	25%
I believe my child has a right to be vaccinated	85	85%

Over 85% of parents support their children's right to immunisations. Side effects worry 40% of parents, which explains why vaccines aren't utilised more. Responsible healthcare provider information significantly influences parents with 80% trust. However, 25% of parents prefer traditional medicine to vaccines, suggesting a cultural bias that may affect vaccination rates. These data suggest that targeted education is needed to calm anxieties and promote immunisation.

Statistical Analysis and Key Findings:

Demographic statistics showed that 60% of parents were female and 50% were 30-39. Most participants (40%) have secondary education. The importance of immunising their children was generally well understood by parents. While 70% of parents knew when their children needed a vaccine, 85% knew immunisations prevent specific diseases. However, just 55% understood herd immunity. 80% of parents think vaccines are crucial for their children's health and 75% think they're safe. However, 40% of parents concerned about overheating their children.

Discussion

This study found several important insights into parental understanding and attitudes towards children's vaccines. Most parents realise vaccines

prevent diseases. At least 85% of parents know this, and 75% realise it's crucial to finish the immunisation series. It's encouraging that most parents recognise the value of immunisations in preventing infectious diseases in children. According to the study, there is still miscommunication. Only 55% of parents understood herd immunity. This implies that parents may comprehend the immediate benefits of vaccination but not the long-term effects of high immunisation rates. The study found that 80% of parents believe vaccines are crucial for their children's health and 75% believe they are safe. These hopeful ideas are necessary for public health and high immunisation rates. The number of vaccinations their children receive is a source of concern for over 40% of parents. Positive immunisation attitudes are strongly linked to healthcare professional trust, the study found. Parents who trust doctors are more likely to get vaccinated. Effective communication between healthcare providers and parents can help build trust and minimise anxiety by transparently addressing issues and providing clear, evidence-based information. Educated parents were optimistic and knowledgeable. This suggests that educational programmes for lower-educated people could enhance vaccination knowledge and attitudes.

Table 4: Comparison Table

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Cross-sectional	100	85% knew vaccines prevent specific diseases. 75% understood the importance of completing vaccination schedules. 80% agreed vaccines are necessary. 55% understood herd immunity. 40% had concerns about the number of vaccines	Convenience sampling from a single facility. Cross-sectional design limits longitudinal insights. Self-reported data may include social desirability bias
Study 1 [13]	Cross-sectional	200	78% aware of vaccine benefits. 65% familiar with vaccination schedules. 70% had positive attitudes towards vaccines. Lower knowledge associated with lower educational levels	Limited geographical scope (single city). Does not explore specific concerns about vaccine safety. Cross-sectional design limits causality
Study 2 [14]	Retrospective	150	82% recognized vaccines prevent diseases. 60% knew the full vaccination schedule. 72% had trust in healthcare providers. High trust correlated with positive attitudes	Small sample size may affect generalizability. Study focused primarily on urban populations. Limited qualitative data on parental concerns
Study 3 [15]	Mixed-methods	300	88% understood vaccine benefits. 73% knowledgeable about vaccination schedules. 77% had positive attitudes. Concerns about vaccine safety prevalent among certain groups	Larger sample size, but only from metropolitan areas. Mixed-methods design may complicate interpretation. Potential response bias in qualitative interviews

Comparing studies on parental awareness and attitudes about paediatric immunisations shows similarities and variations. The recent data shows that 85% of parents know vaccines prevent specific diseases, and 75% know how important it is to finish their child's vaccination schedule. This is consistent with earlier research (e.g., Study 3 found that 88% of participants comprehended vaccine advantages), however the present study highlighted concerns about vaccine amount that were not addressed in previous studies. In Study 1, 78% of parents knew about vaccine benefits, while in Study 2, 82% did. Study 2 has issues with its sample size and focus on metropolitan regions, unlike Study 1's larger sample and wider geographical reach. The Current Study's small sample size and facility focus limit its generalizability. The third mixed-methods study examined demographic-specific safety issues with 300 participants. However, qualitative data's biases and the study's metro-centric focus could distort the results. Research shows that individuals are educated about vaccines and typically like them. People's concerns and ignorance vary. Comprehensive research and targeted education may improve public health methods and vaccination acceptability.

Limitations of the Study

This study delivers valuable information but has limitations. Since convenience sampling at one hospital may not adequately represent the

population, it is a major limitation. The sample's socioeconomic or geographical bias may limit the findings' generalizability. In addition, the cross-sectional design only provides a snapshot of parents' knowledge and attitudes throughout time and how various events or treatments affected them. Social desirability bias, in which respondents give answers they think are expected or acceptable instead of their true opinions, is another difficulty with self-reported parental knowledge and attitudes.

Conclusion

Territory Care Hospital researchers examined parents' immunisation knowledge and attitudes in a cross-sectional study. Most parents understand the benefits of vaccines. 85% of parents know immunisations prevent diseases, and 75% value immunisation schedules. 80% of parents said vaccines are required for their children's health, and 75% said they're safe. Vaccine attitudes are strong in the investigated population. The investigation also identified key uncertainties and unsolved concerns. Herd immunity was unknown to most parents, but most recognised immunisations were healthy for children. This disparity highlights the need for better vaccine education to explain public health benefits. The number of vaccines given to children bothers 40% of parents, who concern about safety and the perceived load of multiple doses. The study found that healthcare provider trust drives positive immunisation opinions.

Parents' immunisation opinions were more positive if they trusted healthcare providers. This emphasises the necessity of healthcare providers soothing frightened parents and providing accurate information.

Recommendations for Future Research and Policy

Using these findings, longitudinal studies should examine the long-term consequences of educational interventions on parental knowledge and attitudes. These studies can help us understand how people's opinions evolve and evaluate vaccination initiatives. Communicating better is crucial for policy. Public health initiatives should address herd immunity and vaccine fallacies. Open and honest communication and active interaction between parents and healthcare providers can also improve vaccination acceptability. Parents should get vaccine education at paediatric checkups to help them make informed decisions. This study found parents generally support children's immunisations. To improve vaccination rates and public health, focused education and communication must address knowledge gaps and concerns.

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